

10.5281/zenodo.7998101

Vol. 06 Issue 06 June - 2023

Manuscript ID: #0869

FAMILY DYSFUNCTION AND PARENTAL ROLE ABDICATION AS PREDISPOSING FACTORS FOR DRUG ABUSE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL ADOLESCENTS AND YOUTHS IN THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, ABUJA, NIGERIA

GIDADO, Bello Kumo & DIFFANG, Abel Dayo

Department of Educational Foundations, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding Email: gbkumo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study aimed at deciphering how factors such as family dysfunction and parental role abdication influence drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. Two objectives, two research questions, and two hypotheses guided the study. A correlation research design was employed to determine the extent of the relationship between the variables. The population of the study was youths within the age range of 18-32 in FCT. A Non-probability sampling technique by opportunity sampling was used to sample 500 young individuals within the age range of 18-32 from major motor parks and markets in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), and some parts of Gwagwalada Area Council. Motor Parks such as Jabi motor park, Area One motor park, Nyanya motor park, and Zuba motor park were selected. While Utako ultra-modern market, Garki model market, Wuse market, and Gwagwlada main market were equally selected for the study. A Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was the main statistic used for data analysis. The instrument for the collection of data was a self-structured questionnaire, validated by experts at the University of Abuja. The results from the analysis show that there is a significant relationship between family dysfunction and a high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory, it equally revealed that there is a significant relationship between parental role abdication and a high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. It was recommended that the Federal Capital Territory Administration should make marriage counseling compulsory for prospective married couples and establish six major offices specifically for counseling within the six area councils in FCT also, families should be guided and equipped with the different types of parenting styles. The Federal Capital Territory Administration in collaboration with the federal government should equally enact stringent laws and penalties if need be for Parental role abdication and drug abuse with strict enforcement, or the existing laws should be strictly enforced.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

1.0 Introduction

The foundation and catalyst that propel most societies to stability, productivity, economic growth, prosperity and greatness is the strength of its youthful population especially a productive one at that. Nigeria is not an exception to that assertion. Consequently, it is said 'charity begins at home'. When parents abdicate their roles and fail with their responsibilities to mould and inculcate in their children the right norms, etiquette, values and belief system that are generally accepted within the society, the young adults become dangerous species to the society manifesting alien, pervasive and uncultured behaviours such as truancy, restiveness, drug abuse, kidnapping, banditry, armed robbery, cultism and fraud amongst others. The parenting style, the socio-economic status and the climate conditions in the home, all affect either negatively or positively the personality of the child (Uwe, 2012). The family is an essential, responsive and fundamental unit of the society with the cardinal responsibility of improving every member of the unit positively for the betterment of the society including those within the immediate environment of the family. Parents are basically the well spring and fountain of every family, hence they are obligated or saddled with responsibilities such as economical, psychological, moral, spiritual which is aimed at improving their offspring and other members within the family unit which goes a long way in improving serenity, productivity and development of the society.

According to Friedman (2016), there are five functions of a family: affective function, socialization function, reproductive function, economic function, and health maintenance function. Obviously, if most of these functions are not adequately catered for by the family it may have adverse effect on the child. The family environment is supposed to provide a conducive and unruffled atmosphere for the holistic development of the child which may go a long way in influencing the social behavior and educational attainment of the child. There are families where functionality is impaired by emotional pressure, stressful and devastating circumstances, such as, depression, death of a loved one in the family, serious or constant illness by parent, separation or divorce, loss of job by either the father or mother, violent conflict by parents, domestic violence and prolonged substance abuse and alcoholism by a parent or both parents amongst others, which may in turn affect their children adversely be it at home, the school environment or within the larger society. Such families could be classified as a dysfunctional family. A dysfunctional family is a family in which conflict, misbehaviour, and often child neglect or abuse on the part of individual parents occurs continually and regularly, leading other members of the family to accommodate such actions (Omare, Kathuri & Kibaara, 2018). They further reiterated that family dysfunction can be any condition that interferes with a normal and healthy family functioning. In dysfunctional families, problems tend to be chronic, stressful and habitual, and children do not consistently get their needs met and equally find it difficult to adjust to the larger society, hence some of them resort into diverse antisocial behaviours including drug usage and abuse.

According to Minullina (2018), the characteristics of a dysfunctional family include but not limited to unharmonious parenting styles, indulging and ignoring a child's need, conflict, hostility, lack of empathy, addiction, lack of communication, mental issues, controlling behaviour, criticism and violence amongst others. In most multicultural societies like Nigeria, parents have specific roles to play in furnishing and inculcating in their children the cultural values of the immediate family, while at the same time harmonising it with the generally accepted societal norms in order for the child to be well adjusted to the society. If the reverse is the case, a situation where the parents failed in performing their roles adequately such children may experience maladjustment right into adulthood. Parental role abdication is a culture-immersed phenomenon with some of its antecedent, outlook,

perception and measurement varying across culture (APA, 2014). Most adolescents and youths involve in drug use and abuse are mostly from dysfunctional families and families where parents have abdicated from their roles leading some of them to waywardness and indulgence in to different forms of antisocial behaviour including drug use and abuse. In Nigeria emphasis on the role and influence of the family on the character of its children, if a male child happened to come from the broken home, he most likely to engage in substance abuse (Aubel, 2012).

2.0 Background

The malaise of family dysfunction and parental role abdication is a major phenomenon and concern of every society including Nigeria. This is because the family is the bedrock and foundation of every society and also the basic factor in determining the developmental and behavioural pattern of an individual being a product of the family. The family is the epicenter in moulding and shaping an individual's behaviour and world view via transmitting the norms and values of the society to the individual since he originates from the family. However, examining closely in Nigeria scenario this proposition seems to be wrong and a hearsay, most especially with the economic upheaval, pressure and recession bedeviling the entire country at present which definitely might have led to diverse issues in many families. There are parents who have abdicated their roles in the family and even ran away and absconded from their responsibilities, dysfunctional families, upbringing in which a child's development is distorted. Such families are driven by emotional pressure, stressful and devastating circumstances, such as, depression, death of a loved one in the family, serious or constant illness by parent, separation or divorce, loss of job by either the father or mother, violent conflict by parents, domestic violence and prolonged substance abuse and alcoholism by a parent or both parents. Children from such dysfunctional background experience severe mental and physical developmental problems; they suffer from psycho-emotional disorders that lead some of them to drug usage and abuse as a mechanism to repress the effect of their vicissitude of which it only ends up in exacerbating their predicament. According to Odigie (2013), a relatively high number of adolescents in Nigeria use hypo-sedatives to cope with stress, stemming from poverty, frustration and parental neglect. This only shows how a dysfunctional family could go a long way in influencing the behavioural pattern of young adults negatively. According to Agwogie (2016), five major predisposing factors of drug abuse are peer pressure, curiosity, ignorance, academic induced frustration and lack of parental care.

According to the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Health (2017), the year's prevalence of any drug use in Nigeria is estimated at 14.4 per cent or 14.3 million people aged between 15 and 64 years. The extent of drug use in Nigeria is comparatively high when compared with the 2016 global annual prevalence of any drug use of 5.6 per cent among the adult population. The past year prevalence of psychoactive substances excluding alcohol, overall was higher among men in Nigeria, however the gender difference in the non-medical use of prescription opioids, tranquilizers and cough syrups was less marked. Drug use was most common among those who were between the ages of 25 and 39 years, while the rates of past year use were lowest among those who were below 24 years of age. Cannabis was the most commonly used drug followed by opioids, mainly the non-medical use of prescription opioids and cough syrup. According to the Chairman, Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), over 19,000 drug offenders have been arrested in 2021, with over 6,000 jailed and more than 12,000 thousand rehabilitated. He equally posited that 5,452 million kilogrammes of drugs valued at 420 billion Naira had been confiscated and 740 hectares of cannabis farm destroyed. He further expresses concern that Nigeria still has a drug prevalence of 14.4 percent which is nearly three times the global average. "We have 15 million Nigerians who are using drugs which is equal to the population of Lesotho, Swaziland, Botswana, Gambia and Liberia all combined". While drug use and

abuse seem to be a quagmire in Nigeria, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) has had its own fair share of this menace. In 2021, The Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) destroyed 20,000 kilogrammes of illicit drugs valued at over 50 billion Naira in FCT, approximately, 19,598 kilogrammes. Comprising 19,178 kilogrammes of cannabis sativa, 0.1 kilogrammes of cocaine, 0.009 kilogrammes of heroin and 420 kilogrammes of other psychotropic substances. While 173 kilogrammes of cocaine, 36 kilogrammes of heroin, 93 kilogrammes ephedrine, 60 kilogrammes of methamphetamine, 50 grammes of cannabis sativa, 219 grammes of rohypnol and 150 grammes of tramadol were seized at Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport Abuja. In 2022, 793 suspects comprising 768 males and 29 females were arrested for drug related cases, 13,125 kilogrammes of different substances and 12,6603 kilogrammes of cannabis sativa were seized. 167 persons were convicted while 78 persons with drug related problems were successfully counselled and rehabilitated within the said period in the FCT.

In the first quarter of 2023 the situation seems to be in the increase. According to The FCT command of NDLEA, 123 suspects of illicit drugs had been arrested within the space of three months (January-March, 2023) 2,265.677 kilogrammes of assorted drugs seized from the suspects, while 20 drug users have been admitted for counselling and rehabilitation in the same period. The command equally said, 13 had been discharged, adding that 142 were in outpatient counselling, with 42 referred from the investigation for counselling. Most of this drug users and abusers are mostly youths who may likely be products of dysfunctional families and families where parents have failed or abdicated their roles right from their childhood leaving them to their mercies, hence it has metamorphosed into a precarious situation to the society. In the findings of Odigie (2013) it was revealed that drug addiction in adolescents is brought about by family instability and other psycho-social trauma in the family. Ryhor (2019) in related research found out that, young people are sometimes exposed to criminality and other vices as a result of family dysfunction hence physically and emotionally addled with the responsibilities of taking care of the family themselves. Schier, Herke, Nickel, Egle, and Hardt (2015) in their study discovered that in the absence of any meaningful direction and guidance from parents, the young are under pressure to take over the family responsibility including financial aspect hence engages in a lot of illegal and criminal behavior in order to sustain the family.

Generally, youths are products of diverse backgrounds with peculiar socio-economic and psychological disparities which could influence their behavioural pattern in the larger society. The family being one of the most fundamental and essential units of the society contributes tremendously to the physical, psychical and spiritual wellbeing of their children which could go a long way to make or mar the young adults behaviour in the future. Hence, youths from dysfunctional families, and families where parents have abdicated their roles in the Federal Capital Territory may experience heightened tension which could be prevalence of diverse criminal tendencies and vices which may lead them to drug usage and abuse. The effect of drug abuse by youths is equally alarming and has diverse implication to almost every aspect of the society be it psychological, social-economical and even health wise. Mamman, Othman & Lian, (2014) in their study discovered that drug abuse is a protracted problem that posed a serious threat on social, economic and health conditions of the individual, family's commonalities, the nations and the entire global world. The study further showed that the persistence abuse of drug led to the increasing crime and delinquency, insurgency and terrorism, the spread of deadly diseases and illnesses such as an increase in the spread of hepatitis B and C virus increase in the spread of HIV /AIDS. The study equally posited that drug abuse habit predisposes the youth to a disease that may lead to early death such as cardiovascular diseases (CVD), lung cancer, tuberculosis and psychosomatic disorders.

In a study conducted by Ibrahim, Amit, Din & Ong (2017), it was revealed that 70 per cent of the substance users engaged in the menace as a result of peer group influence and it is due to improper care 28 per cent by their parents led them to abuse drug. In another related study conducted by Shehu and Rao P.D. (2020), in South-west states of Nigeria, on the effects of drug abuse on mental disorder among prison inmates and psychiatric hospital. 70 respondents were purposefully selected 50 among psychiatric patients and 20 among the prison inmates and were interviewed and the finding was analyzed using descriptive survey. The finding revealed that drugs mostly abused were Tramadol, Diazepam, marijuana and codeine type syrup. Anxiety, depression, neurosis and schizophrenia are the mental disorders the patients suffer with. Heart attack, respiratory tract infections, and neurological disease are the major health impairment the patients are suffering with. This study shows the catastrophic effect of drug use among youths in South-west, Nigeria. The consequence of drug use is not only detrimental to the user alone but could also affect non-user especially, the toxic smoke emanating from the burning cigarettes which the environmental health professionals' term it as "second-hand smoke, or Environmental Tobacco Smoke (ETS)". This discharged smoke carried significant concentrations of "ammonia, carbon monoxide, nicotine and tar than do the smoke inhaled by the smoker". ETS is responsible for the death of over 50,000 people annually (Cicchetti & Handley, 2019). Parsons reported abusing heroin was discovered to have suffered from "dependence, blood-borne viruses' psychological abnormalities (Njoku, Harvey, & Jason, 2017).

2.1 Purpose

The purpose of this study is to ascertain family dysfunction and parental role abdication as predisposing factors for drug abuse among youths in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

The specific objectives were:

- a. to determine the relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory
- b. to determine the relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse in the Federal Capital Territory.

2.2 Hypothesis

Based on the objectives of this study the following null hypotheses were raised at 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in Federal Capital Territory.

H02: There is no significant relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse among youths in Federal Capital Territory.

3.0 Research Methodology

3.1 Population and Sample

The study adopted a correlation research design to determine the extent of the relationship of the variables. Non-probability sampling technique by opportunity sampling was used to select 500 young individuals within the age range of 18-32 from major motor parks and markets in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), and some parts of Gwagwalada Area Council. Motor parks such as Jabi motor park, Area one motor park, Nyanya motor park and Zuba motor park were selected. While Utako ultra-modern market, Garki model market, Wuse market and Gwagwalada main market were equally selected for the study.

3.2 Data and Sources of Data

The instrument that was used for collection of data in this research was a self-structured questionnaire “family dysfunction, parental role abdication and high rate of drug in FCT, Abuja Questionnaire (FDPRADAQ)”. The questionnaire was divided into three sections; section (A) contained personal information of the respondents, section (B) comprised of statements on relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory, section (C) consisted of statements on the relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse in the Federal Capital Territory. The questionnaire was designed and validated following the Likert scale type. The instrument was tested for validity by different researchers in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education university of Abuja to ensure that the items relate to the purpose and objectives of the study.

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, the instrument was pilot-tested by the researcher using individuals ranging from age 18-32 within the study area who were not part of the main study. 30 copies of the questionnaire were distributed within the area of study, but outside the main study environment. The testing was aimed at establishing if the items in the questionnaire were relevant and could be used again for same purpose. Data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha statistics in order to determine the internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The instrument yielded a reliability index of 0.77.

3.3 Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by social learning theory also known as observational learning as postulated by Albert Bandura (1977). In Albert Bandura’s Bobo Doll Experiment of 1961, Children were able to observe two different adult models, one aggressive and the other non-aggressive behaviours when allowed to play with the bobo doll, most especially if the model earned a reward for his behaviour. This demonstrated that children do learn through observation of adult behaviour be it positive or negative. According to Bandura (1977), people are products of past learning experience and all human behaviour develops from past social stimulus event. Bandura maintained that some behaviours can be learned only through the exposure to models. Bandura describes modeling and observational behaviours of people through the following process: (1) First, the person picks up on a modeling behaviour and the actions that are related to a specific activity, (2) what has been observed could serve to elicit the performance of similar responses conceived through various cognitive processes in a certain way by the model, (3) following, the model’s behaviour could influence the performance of socially deviant behaviour of the individual while the viewer attempts to translate his conceptions into actions, and (4) finally, the person is motivated even more so if he receives positive feedback for his actions. The observer’s inhibition of performing or imitating the model’s behaviour is sequence to the behaviour being strengthen or weakened through reinforcement either positive or negative reinforcements.

This process on one hand increases the self-efficacy of the achiever. On the other hand, when achievements are made by people with high self-efficacy, they tend to perform better (Bandura, 1977). Self-efficacy is coined by Bandura (1977) as a “theory of behavioral change” and describes a person’s belief in himself, in his capabilities in his actions. It plays a significant role in the “triadic reciprocal causation” model influencing how people behave, make decisions, react to changes, cope with challenges, and accomplish things in their life (Bandura, 1977). The higher the self-efficacy, the easier it is for a person to deal with the challenges he will face in life, such as change, failure, or even more dramatic events such as dealing with health problems, trauma, or even death. Efficacy

expectations can vary in magnitude based on the level of difficulty of the task, in generality and strength. Bandura further described that efficacy beliefs affect the way people function through four major procedures: the way they think, the way they are motivated in the sense based on the level of efficacy they will decide what they can achieve in life, the way they feel, affecting their emotional and mental wellbeing, and finally the decisions they make (Bandura, 1977). Self-regulation entails guiding oneself by deciding how to act and what to circumvent while facing challenges and that encompasses moral conduct (Bandura, 1977).

The relevance of this theory to this research work cannot be underestimated. This theory provided a framework on how parents can easily influence their children in the family through observing, imitating and modeling their attitudes, behaviours and emotional disposition. This theory is very pertinent to this research work since it demonstrates that all the behavioural and emotional characteristics by parents are well observed by their children and could be model by them. When there's conflict, hostility, lack of empathy, drug abuse and addiction, breached communication, mental issues, criticism and violence amongst members of the family, inability for parents to perform their roles adequately, such instability or dysfunctionality in the family is being observed and could be imitated or influence children who grew up from such family background. When parents use or abuse drugs or in some cases send their children to purchase cigarette or hard drugs for them, they should have it at the back of their mind that, they are sending the wrong signal to them, because children from such homes may end up as chain smokers or even drug abusers and addicts. Parents are supposed to be role models to their children. The proponent of this theory showcased that parents must always imbibe and inculcate in their children the right societal values through social and observational learning from childhood as role models and also the first point of contact to the children within the societal enclave. If family dysfunction and parental role abdication are some of the predisposing factors for drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory, then social learning theory is very adequate for this study, it has also been used by many researchers in different societal studies because of its importance.

3.4 Statistical Tools

3.4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The data obtained through the use of research instrument were subjected to statistical analysis in tabular form using appropriate statistical analysis. Simple percentages, frequency count and mean score were used for demographic data and the research questions. The hypothesis were tested by the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Pearson Product Moment Correlation is considered suitable because it allows for the determination of the relationship in the mean responses of the respective groups.

4.0 Results

The analysis based on the formulated hypothesis is presented thus:

H01: There is no significant relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory.

Variables	X	SD	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-cal	r-crit
Family dysfunction	2.23	1.51	21.22	54.24			
High rate of Drug abuse	2.86	1.66	28.22	86.68	68.22	0.1646	0.1024

*=significant at 0.05 level (p<0.05)

Data on table 1 represents the group statistics and analysis carried out to examine the relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. The mean value of family dysfunction is 2.23 with standard deviation of 1.51 while the mean value for high rate of drug abuse is 2.86 with standard deviation of 1.66. The r-cal (.16) is greater than r-crit (.10) at 0.05 level of significance indicating a significant linear correlation of the two variables. This reveals that there is significant relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory.

Variables	X	SD	Σx	Σx^2	Σxy	r-cal	r-crit
parental role abdication	2.16	1.50	21.02	51.22			
High rate of Drug abuse	2.86	1.66	28.22	86.68	64.06	0.3473	0.1024

*=significant at 0.05 level (p<0.05)

Data on table 2 represents the group statistics and analysis carried out to examine the relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. The mean value of parental role abdication is 2.16 with standard deviation of 1.50 while the mean value for high rate of drug abuse is 2.86 with standard deviation of 1.66. The r-cal (.34) is greater than r-crit (.10) at 0.05 level of significance indicating a significant linear correlation of the two variables. This reveals that there is significant relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory.

5.0 Discussion of Findings

The result in table 1 revealed that there is significant relationship between family dysfunction and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. This is in line with Ryhor (2019) who asserted that young people are sometimes exposed to criminality and other vices as a result of family dysfunction hence physically and emotionally addled with the responsibilities of taking care of the family themselves. Also corroborating the findings of this study is Odigie (2013), whose study revealed that drug addiction in adolescents is brought about by family instability and other psycho-social trauma in the family. The result in table 2 equally revealed that there is significant relationship between parental role abdication and high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. This is in conformity with a study conducted by Ibrahim, Amit, Din & Ong (2017),

which revealed that 70 per cent of the substance users engaged in the menace as a result of peer group influence and it is due to improper care 28 per cent by their parents led them to abuse drug. Schier et al (2015), equally concurred by concluding that in the absence of any meaningful direction and guidance from parents, the young are under pressure to take over the family responsibility including financial aspect hence engages in a lot of illegal and criminal behavior in order to sustain the family. Also, in a study of 542 middle school students from the Birmingham Youth Violence Study in Alabama, USA, poor parenting practices (e.g. less nurturance and harsh and inconsistent discipline) was found to be strongly related to school- level alcohol and cigarette use (Mrug, Gains, Su& Windle 2010).

6.0 Conclusion

The high rate of Drug abuse in the Federal Capital Territory has become a cankerworm that is eaten deep in to the fabric of Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory begging for solution with immediatealacrity. The family is supposed to be the astute pillar and foundation in providing an enabling and conducive environment for children to explore and strive right from home before entangling or mixing up with the general society. The family is supposed to inculcate into their children the virtues that comes with its culture while also, considering the generally accepted norms of the society. With the high rate of diverse social vices today in the country coupled with social and emotional pressure faced by most youths pushing them into crime and criminality, family dysfunction and parental role abdication is a major concern adding more salt in the already existing injury, hence high rate of drug abuseamong youths in the Federal Capital Territory.

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that family dysfunction has tremendous effect on the high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. Parental role abdication equally contributes to the high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. This only implies that, if the Federal Capital Territory administration do not want Abuja to turn to a drug dungeon for our teeming youths, family dysfunctionality and parental role abdication should be overwhelmingly addressed with the urgency that it deserves, the recommendations in this study.

7.0 Implications of findings for Parents, Society and Education

The findings of this study have several implications to parents, society and education. Among these are: parents from dysfunctional families tend to influence drug use and abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory which have adverse effect on the society. This by implication means that, if the issues surrounding dysfunctionality within the familyare not swiftly addressed with the seriousness that it deserves, eradicating drug use and abuse among youths in the FCT will be a 'wild goose chase'.

Parental role abdication has equally shown to have tremendous effect on high rate of drug abuse among youths in the Federal Capital Territory. This by implication means that, if the FCT administration fail in formulating stringent policies or laws, or the existing ones are not implemented to curtail Parental role abdication within the Federal Capital Territory, the scorch of drug use and abuse among youths in the FCT will continue unabated which could be detrimental to the society at large.

Most youths are from diverse family background within the society. after leaving their immediate family environment the converge within the educational environment with the purpose of being equipped with the general accepted norms, etiquette and value system of the society. Thus, the family is expected to have set the pace for the young adult moral foundation and also inculcate the culture and value system of the immediate family to the young adult. Young adults who grew up in a

dysfunctional family as well as one whose parent abdicated its role will certainly be robbed of the virtue of a functional family hence, most of them engage in different criminal and antisocial behaviours such as armed robbery, negative self-esteem, fraudulent activities, drug use and abuse, cultism amongst others. This by implication means that, schools in FCT particularly higher institutions of learning must be proactive to identify young adults from such families, and measures should be put in place to address the predicament. Failure to put in place mechanisms to address the adverse effect of drug use and abuse among youths in the FCT which is ticking time bomb, may have adverse damage on our education in FCT.

8.0 Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made from this research work. Federal Capital Territory Administration should make marriage counselling compulsory for prospective married couples and establish six major offices specifically for counselling within the six area councils in FCT and also, parents should be guided and equipped with the different types of parenting styles. The Federal Capital Territory Administration in collaboration with the federal government should equally enact stringent laws and penalties if need be for Parental role abdication and drug abuse with strict enforcement or the existing laws should be strictly enforced.

References

- Agwogie M. (2016). Drug abuse and Nigerian youths. Vanguard Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2016/06/drug-abuse-and-nigerian-youths>.
- American Psychological Association (2014). *The Adolescent* (online). Available. <http://www.apa.org/adolescent>.
- Aubel, J. (2012). The role and influence of grandmothers on child nutrition.
- Bandura, A. (1977). Social learning theory. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191-215. doi:10.1037/0033-295x.84.2.191.
- Cicchetti, D., & Handley, E. D. (2019). Child maltreatment and the development of substance use and disorder. *Neurobiology of stress*, 10, 100144.
- Friedman, M.M. (2016). Family Nursing: Theory and Practice. California: Appleton & Lange.
- Ibrahim, N., Amit, N., Din, N. C., & Ong, H. C. (2017). Gender differences and psychological factors associated with suicidal ideation among youth in Malaysia. *Psychology research and behavior management*, 10, 129.
- Mamman, H., Othman, A. T., & Lian, L. H. (2014). Adolescent's and drugs abuse in Nigeria. *Journal of biology, agriculture and healthcare*, 4(1), 5-9.
- Minullina, A. F, (2018). Psychological Trauma of children of Dysfunctional families. 4th International forum on Teacher Education. *The European proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences*. ISSN: 2357-1330.
- Mrug, S., Gaines J., Su W., and Windle M. (2010). School-Level Substance Use: Effects on Early Adolescents' Alcohol, Tobacco, and Marijuana Use. *Journal of studies on Alcohol and Drugs*. Vol. 71(4): 488-495.
- NDLEA Destroyed Drugs Worth N50 billion in Abuja. The Guardian news Paper, November 30th 2021. Nigeria, Federal Ministry of Health, National Policy for Controlled Medicines, 2017.
- Nigerian drug users more than population of four African countries- Marwa. Daily Post newspaper November 3rd, 2022.
- Njoku, M. G. C., Harvey, R., & Jason, L. A. (2017). Substance Use Aftercare Services in Nigeria: Proposing Oxford House Model. *GOUNI Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 3, 1-10.
- Odigie, J. I. (2013). Engendering family stability with adolescent stress counselling Intervention. A paper presented at an International Association of Nigeria (CASSON) OAU, Ile-Ife 27th-31st August pg 1-7.
- Omare, A.O. Kathuri, N.J. & Kibaara T. (2018). Effects of dysfunctional families on public

secondary school students' academic performance in habaswein sub county, Wajir county, kenya. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Literature*.

Ryhor, T. (2019). The Dysfunctional family as a factor of Juvenile Delinquency Formation: Actual problems in the Republic of Belarus. *Pro Justitia*. <https://ejournals.lib.auth.gr/projustitiahttps://doi.org/10.26262/pj.v210.7500>

Schier, K., Herke, M., Nickel, R., Egle, U. T., Hardt, J. (2015). Long-Term Sequence of Emotional Parentification: A cross-validation study using sequences of regression. *Journal of childfamily studies* 24, 1307-1321. Doi: 10:1007/510826-014-9938-z (googlescholar).

Shehu, H., & Rao, P. D. (2020). Sociology of Covid-19: people perceptions regarding the outbreak of the pandemic among people of Northern, Nigeria. *Sustainable Humanosphere*, 16(1), 2078-2089.

Uwe, E.A. (2012), Pre-marital and marital therapy as family homeostasis and counselling strategy for enhancing Societal security: in Keynote and lead presentations at the annual international conference of the counselling Association of Nigeria. Kolo I.A (ed). Pg 26-31.

2,256kg of Drugs Seized 123 nabbed in Abuja: NDLEA. Peoples Gazette, News Agency of Nigeria, April 17, 2023.

793 Drug Suspects Arrested in FCT in 2022: NDLEA. SaharaReporters, March 7th, 2023.